

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ENHANCING TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL SKILLS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract: This article discusses the distinctive qualities of enhancing teachers' professional skills in the higher education system and the factors contributing to their development.

Key concepts: psychological factors, pedagogical erudition, goal-orientation, practical thinking, pedagogical-psychological tact, professional observation skills, communicativeness, psychological-pedagogical reflection.

In our republic, we are witnessing that issues related to the development of education and the future of young people, who are the heirs of our future, are considered one of the highest priority areas. The state is providing care for the education and upbringing of the younger generation.

The reason is that education and upbringing have been considered matters of life and death in the development of humanity. The issue of security also depends on education. Therefore, countries around the world view this issue as a national concern. It is no exaggeration to say that the fundamental reform of the education system has become the most important factor and solid foundation for changing the consciousness, mindset, and worldview of our people, increasing their political and civic engagement, and strengthening their confidence in the future. Our new generation - educated youth free from all the vices of the past - is today becoming the decisive driving force for the democratization and liberalization of our country, its renewal and sustainable development.

The implementation of these complex and important tasks depends on the professional skills of pedagogical staff, their ability to manage the student body and exert psychological influence on them. Because ..."the professional level of teachers and professors is their specialized knowledge. In this regard, it is necessary to create an environment that actively promotes the processes of education, spiritual and intellectual development, and the formation of true values" [1].

In this sense, a teacher's professional skills represent their unique individual-psychological structure, serving as one of the factors ensuring the effectiveness of professional activity in the "human-human" system. These skills comprise cognitive and practical components, psychological knowledge, professional thinking, and practical skills and abilities necessary for establishing interpersonal communication and exerting psychological influence.

The problem of researching professional skills has been studied and developed in the scientific works of numerous psychologists and pedagogical scientists, including S.L. Rubinstein, A.N. Leontiev, B.G. Ananyev, E.A. Klimov, A.I. Alekseev, T.V. Kudryavtsev, R.Z. Gainutdinov, E.G. Goziev, G.B. Shoumarov, B.R. Rakhmonkulov, S.V. Asyamov, E.Yu. Agzamova,

and R.M. Makhmudov. In these works, the principle of unity of consciousness and activity was approached as a fundamental category.

It is recognized that human professional development is a long-term, multifaceted, and dynamic process that progresses through four stages. These are: Stage 1 - professional intention; Stage 2 - education and upbringing; Stage 3 - entering the profession; and Stage 4 - professional mastery [2].

For the successful implementation of pedagogical activity, personal qualities such as reflexivity, communicativeness, and cooperation are important and necessary for a teacher [3].

According to some scholars (A.K. Makarova, M.G. Davletshin, E.G. Goziev, and others), the most important professional skills of a teacher are complemented by pedagogical erudition, goal-orientation, practical thinking, pedagogical-psychological tact, professional observation, the ability to listen, the capacity to make correct decisions in various non-standard situations, psychological forecasting, and psychological-pedagogical reflection. These qualities of a teacher are manifested in harmony with their professional abilities in relation to pedagogical activity.

The components of a teacher's professional skills are inextricably linked, forming a holistic system of internal (subjective) and external (objective) structures.

In the development of a teacher's professional skills, their adaptation to their profession is of great importance. From this perspective, adaptation is multifaceted and is divided into psychophysiological, socio-psychological, and professional adaptations [4].

Each teacher possesses these three types of adaptation, which serve to guide students towards the profession and help to reveal specific problems and difficulties.

The following can be cited as the main reasons for teachers' adaptation to their profession. Including:

- inability to process work-related information in a timely manner; if it can be processed promptly, the ability to quickly adapt or orient oneself to the new environment and situation;
- lack of experience in professional activities;
- solving several tasks simultaneously, such as studying the environment, making decisions, and directly consulting with experienced managers and mentors about one's behavior;
- creating a positive impression of oneself in others, sometimes being able to convince employees about oneself, and so on [5].

Psychophysiological adaptation is a specific type of adaptation involving the physical and psychophysiological adjustment of the educator's body to new conditions, for example, to a new routine, lifestyle, sanitary and hygienic environment, and the specifics of organizing nutrition and rest.

adaptation reaction causes psychological tension and indicates fitness or unfitness for future activity. To overcome negative situations arising in psychophysiological adaptation, factors such as the teacher's positive emotional-volitional state, quick adaptation to the work schedule, proper distribution of workload, and others are considered important.

Socio-psychological adaptation - is the adaptation of young teachers to the social environment at their new workplace. This involves adjusting to a new team, new personalities, new professional interactions, and adapting to new traditions, as well as integrating oneself into a new collective.

In socio-psychological adaptation, there is a generally accepted view that while the teacher studies the collective, they also become accustomed to it, as it can sometimes be difficult for the collective to accept the teacher.

Sometimes, disagreements arise between the teacher and other members of the team for various reasons. However, in such situations, the teacher must adhere to "professional etiquette," which will demonstrate their cultural awareness and, if necessary, their correctness.

In the teacher's adaptation to the collective environment, the chosen profession, the ethnopsychology of citizens, and the people around them also play their own roles. The following factors can contribute to effective adaptation:

- satisfaction with the place of work and the chosen profession;
- employment (service) and integration into the team.

The result of a teacher's satisfaction or dissatisfaction with their work is primarily reflected in the outcomes of their work.

Satisfaction with one's work and activities depends on many factors, such as the workload, workplace location, weather conditions, noise levels, lighting, temperature, colleagues' attitudes, leadership style, salary, opportunities for career advancement, daily routine, and incentives.

During the teacher's adaptation to work, conflict situations often arise, and practical assistance in resolving these conflicts is always necessary.

Professional adaptation - this adaptation occurs directly during the teacher's professional activity, during the internship period (6 months or 1 year) and helps develop skills. Those who cannot adapt will likely change professions.

In the formation of a teacher as a proficient specialist, it is crucial to first develop socio-psychological and professional qualities, such as willpower, the ability to foster a positive attitude towards work, the capacity to solve problems independently, self-confidence, and practical experience, among others.

Professional activity is consistently associated with stress or excessive workload, which gradually affects the teacher's mental state. In a teacher's adaptation to professional activity, the influence of surrounding colleagues, mentors, and experienced educators certainly plays a role. For instance, after working in the same position and profession for several years, a teacher inevitably experiences professional burnout (manifested in changes to character, behavior, and speech). Fatigue, exhaustion, monotonous work, and stress contribute to this condition.

Fatigue, in turn, is reflected in the teacher's attitude towards their work and in their behavior, making them more prone to conflicts. The extent of such fatigue varies among teachers, with some experiencing it more than others. Fatigue or exhaustion is a natural phenomenon, inherent to the physiological, psychological, and biological structure of a teacher's personality. Fatigue can be temporary, and it's natural for it to progress into a state of exhaustion.

Fatigue has a direct negative impact on work performance; during this period, an individual's productivity decreases, physical strength diminishes, and muscle endurance declines. This process is also directly observed in the weakening of memory, perception, sensation, and attention. Prolonged fatigue leads to persistent exhaustion.

Excessive fatigue leads to stress, neurosis, and somatic conditions. As a result, psychogenic disorders of character arise, and unnecessary conflicts increase. When fatigued, rest-related behaviors don't always yield sufficient results.

Fatigue, in turn, creates monotony in an individual's activities. Monotony is the uniformity in activity. It arises from repeating the same task several or even hundreds of times, sometimes including high-paced work. Monotony is characterized by a preference for sleep, boredom, and lack of interest in work.

The basis for eliminating monotony is to introduce changes in work, most importantly, altering the work rhythm. By eliminating monotony, interest in work, life, and profession emerges. Another factor is psychological strain. This strain is undoubtedly rooted in difficulties and conflicts, which primarily contribute to disrupting the existing positive environment.

In adaptation, the teacher must first take into account the students' readiness for professional activity, as well as the specifics of the workplace.

There are also forms and methods that help educators adapt to the profession. These are:

- a) Conducting psychological and psychophysiological examinations of young teachers, providing characteristics based on the results, and explaining adaptation conditions.
- b) Providing recommendations based on examination results.
- c) Organizing group consultations and developing the skill of transforming these consultations into socio-psychological training.
- g) Teaching how to regulate mental and emotional state before performing any task or assignment.
- d) This training should primarily involve employees with weak emotional and volitional states.

In the adaptation of young teaching staff to the environment, there are complex tasks that need to be addressed, for example:

1. The ability to make decisions.
2. The art of organizing activities.
3. Monitoring task completion.
4. Regulating work relationships.

Adaptation - that is, professional adaptation - is a difficult and multifaceted activity and is also a unique method of self-development that requires constant attention from the employee.

From this perspective, the following factors are important in the formation of a teacher's professional skills. These are:

- Having information about each student's individual psychological characteristics, temperament, abilities, character strengths and weaknesses, and achievements and shortcomings in their activities;
- Good understanding of the socio-psychological environment in the team, and knowledge of the psychological characteristics of the student-teacher relationship;
- Being aware of the most convenient and modern teaching methods, the ability to use them effectively, having the skills to implement new innovative technologies in the educational process, psychologically analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of one's activities, improving the quality and effectiveness of one's work, practicing self-control,

enhancing professional knowledge, and mastering the most effective methods of self-improvement at a high level [6].

A teacher's professional skills are manifested not only in their attitude towards learners but also in the organization of their personal pedagogical activities. Due to not knowing their inner potential, the teacher copies the experience of colleagues and begins to imitate them.

In this sense, it is advisable to use the following methods in developing a teacher's professional skills in the educational process. These include:

- Organizing socio-psychological trainings on improving the teacher's professional skills, developing mental processes (professional memory, attention, perception, logical thinking, etc.), forming professional knowledge, abilities, and skills, and mastering psychological methods of stress relief;
- Analyzing psychological situations to collaboratively resolve issues related to professional activities (low academic performance, conflict situations in the group);
- Studying at the "school for enhancing young teachers' skills" to improve the professional competence of the teacher;
- Improvement of personal qualities (such as skills in analyzing one's pedagogical activity, "mental training," and "brainstorming") that are crucial for a teacher to fully realize their potential in their professional activity.

The main factors in developing a teacher's pedagogical skills are, firstly, the teacher's self-formation as a specialist, and secondly, self-awareness as a person. A teacher's pedagogical skills are not formed uniformly, but throughout their professional career. Monitoring this dynamic process allows for its adequate assessment, predicting its development and the growth of the teacher's personality. The teacher's personal and professional qualities are intertwined with their abilities.

These characteristics of the teaching profession are reflected in its professionogram.

The professional professionogram of a teacher is expressed in the following:

- psychological characteristics of the teacher's personality;
- requirements for the teacher's psychological and pedagogical training;
- scope and content of specialized training;
- content of methodological training in the specialty.

In turn, the psychological competencies of the teacher's personality are manifested in the following areas. Specifically:

In the ideological sphere: scientific worldview and beliefs; deep understanding of social needs and moral imperatives; awareness of social and civic duty; socio-political engagement.

In the field of the teaching profession: love for learners and motivation to work with them, interest in pedagogical activity; psychological and pedagogical acuity and observational skills, pedagogical tact, pedagogical imagination; organizational abilities; fairness; sincerity; demandingness; determination and goal-orientation; composure; self-control; professional competence.

cognitive sphere includes a broad scientific outlook, spiritual needs and interests, intellectual curiosity, the ability to sense novelty; the desire to enhance pedagogical knowledge. For effective pedagogical activity, the teacher must possess the following types of abilities:

- Cognitive ability;
- Ability to explain educational materials;
- Observational ability;
- Verbal ability;
- Organizational ability;
- Ability to earn respect;
- Ability to communicate effectively;
- Ability to foresee the future;
- Ability to distribute attention.

In conclusion, it can be said that a teacher's reputation is primarily manifested in their dedication to their profession. Only then can the teacher set an example for learners through their practical activities and instill confidence in themselves. These qualities are an important factor in the education, upbringing, and professional training of young people. Indeed, awakening a sense of responsibility for the fate of the Homeland, cherishing the Homeland as a sacred place, and teaching them to live with a sense of belonging to their surroundings is the sacred duty of every teacher..

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